

Tourist mobility:

Characteristics and differentiation from everyday mobility

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Core results

The aim of this paper is to provide a concise categorisation of tourism mobility and to build a bridge between transport and tourism research. To this end, a two-dimensional model of mobility is presented that illustrates the different forms of mobility in everyday life and tourism. The model shows that the boundaries between everyday mobility and tourist mobility are fluid and that a view of tourist mobility based purely on everyday journeys is inaccurate. As their destinations, frequencies and distances can differ greatly, the modelling of traffic flows and needs must take into account the temporal, spatial and organisational differences between everyday and tourist mobility.

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Introduction

From a traditional perspective, tourism consists of two components: Mobility and stay (Cohen, 1974). In the real world, the matter is more complicated because movement can take very different forms (McKercher & Zoltan, 2014): As a journey between home and destination, as a detour on arrival and departure, during local mobility or as part of a round trip, where there is not one but many destinations (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Itinerary types

Source: McKercher & Zoltan, 2014, p. 35, 37

In this working paper, we want to take a closer look at this mobility component. We are looking less at the technical component of mobility and more at the social science component: "Mobility is movement made meaningful in any given social context" (Duncan, 2012, p. 114).

The distinction between everyday and tourist mobility is a fundamental necessity when studying tourist behaviour. Tourist mobility is analysed from various perspectives, for example with regard to the choice of means of transport (Bünstorf, 2022; Dütschke et al., 2022; Gross & Grimm, 2018), the emissions and climate impact of tourist mobility (Gössling et al., 2017; Mailer et al., 2019) or the long-term volume development (Frick et al., 2014; Schmücker et al., 2023).

The aim of this document is a concise and pragmatic categorisation of tourism mobility and its differentiation from everyday mobility. In doing so, we also want to build a bridge between transport research, which often focusses on route purposes, and tourism research, which focusses on destinations.

Tourism

The generally accepted definition of tourism today comes from the UN Statistical Office and the World Tourism Organisation. It was developed in 2008 to harmonise tourism statistics worldwide (*International*

*Recommendation for Tourism Statistics, IRTS 2008*¹). The core definition is as follows:

"A visitor is a traveller taking a trip to a main destination outside his/her usual environment, for less than a year, for any main purpose (business, leisure or other personal purpose) other than to be employed by a resident entity in the country or place visited. These trips taken by visitors qualify as tourism trips. Tourism refers to the activity of visitors."(United Nations Statistics Division (UNSD) & United Nations World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO), 2010)

The IRTS 2008 therefore regard 'travel' as a the broader term² and 'visitor' as a part of it. This was not always the case. Erik Cohen (1974, p. 530) still juxtaposed 'travel' (the movement) and 'visitor' (the stay). He thus goes back to Daniel Boorstin (1962) who stated that the character of 'travel' (from the French "travail") is active and that of 'tourism' is passive.

'Leaving one's usual environment' is a central aspect in the IRTS 2008 definition of tourism. In the German-speaking discussion, this aspect is directly linked to the term 'Fremdenverkehr' (literally meaning 'traffic of foreigners'): tourism arises through the travelling and stay of non-

¹ The Eurostat methodological handbook on tourism statistics is identical on these points (Eurostat, 2014).

² Section 2.4: Travel refers to the activity of travellers. A traveller is someone who moves between different geographical locations for any purpose and any duration.

residents.³ This idea of ‘a tourist is someone who is not a resident’ is still relevant today (Mor et al., 2023).

At the same time, however, it also emphasises the extraordinary and unusual aspects of tourism.

”tourism connotes a change from routine, something different, strange, unusual or novel, an experience“ (Cohen, 1974, pp. 531-532).

The Eurostat definition of tourism (2014, p. 31) provides further indications in that tourism only exists if the purpose of the trip is ‘not in the current life routine/not to maintain the daily living’. Tourism can therefore be assumed when money is spent rather than earned. This perspective also has a long tradition.⁴ However, it is no longer uncontroversial since researchers have been thinking about a ‘New Mobilities Paradigm’. This paradigm wants to see the old normal (sedentarism: housing and stability) replaced by a new normal of deterritorialisation, nomadism and permanent ‘on the move’ (Sheller &

³ ‘Tourism (is) the totality of relationships and phenomena resulting from the travel and stay of persons for whom the place of stay is neither the main and permanent place of residence nor work.’ (Kaspar, 1975, p. 13).

‘Tourism is the epitome of all those and, first and foremost, all economic processes that are directly connected with the influx, lingering and outflow of foreigners to, in and from a particular community, country or state.’ (von Schullern, 1911, p. 434).

‘Tourism should therefore only include the traffic of people staying in hotels and guesthouses for less than a week - in health resorts and seaside resorts, guests who stay there for more than a week

Urry, 2006; Spode, 2017). Duncan (2012, p. 113) concludes: ”Increasingly tourism is seen as constitutive of everyday life.“

Cohen (1974, p. 533) limited his definition of ‘tourist’ to purely leisure travellers who travelled for pleasure. Today, travelling for business or education is clearly part of the definition of tourism. Nevertheless, some purposes of travelling are likely to cause uncertainty about the classification of travel as tourism. Examples include pilgrimages, trips by volunteers, hospital stays, *gap years* or a stay abroad after leaving school, trips to visit family, etc. Cohen calls such ambiguous journeys ‘partial tourist rôles’.

Such demarcation problems can also arise with day trips: Is shopping in a Swedish furniture store still everyday life or already tourism? The same question applies to stays in a second home or on a permanent caravan site. The distinction becomes particularly complicated when a trip has several purposes: Is a visit to the doctor followed by a tour to a museum in the next largest city tourism or not?

are also considered ‘foreigners’ (Warnecke, 1921, p. 11), all three quotes translated from German by the authors

⁴ ”first, that absence from home is relatively short, and second, that money spent during absence is money derived from home and not earned in the places visited.” (Ogilvie, 1934)

‘A certain breakthrough was achieved at the Delegates’ Conference for the Promotion of Tourism in the Austrian Alpine Countries in 1894, at which the ‘tourist industry’ was defined in economic terms for the first time: It leads the consumer to goods ‘which are not transportable’, such as the mountains and the climate, and ‘thus transforms previously unused goods into economic goods’, as the conference president Josef Stradner explained.’ (Spode, 2012), translated by the authors

It becomes apparent that it is not always possible to make a clear distinction: While certain trips are clearly non-touristy (such as daily shopping, travelling to work or school), others are clearly touristy (such as the annual holiday trip). In between, however, there is no sharp distinction, but rather a continuum between everyday life and tourism, so that the boundary can shift depending on the perspective and purpose of the observation.

This distinction between everyday and tourist mobility should not be confused with the frequency of use of means of transport, which is often surveyed in mobility-related studies. It is true that a means of transport that is used 'daily or almost daily' is certainly (also) used in everyday life. However, this says nothing about its use for tourism, because the high frequency of everyday use may overshadow the lower frequency of use for tourism.

Time utilisation and mobility purposes

In mobility research, journeys are categorised according to how time is used. For example, the "Mobility in Germany" (MiD) study categorises the following seven journey purposes⁵ :

1. Work (journey to the workplace)
2. On business (journeys during working hours)
3. Education
4. Shopping
5. Errands (for example a visit to the doctor or a visit to the authorities)
6. Leisure time
7. Accompaniment (for example, a mother has taken her child to school).

The MiD is a Germany-wide survey on everyday mobility and differentiates between various transport purposes, see (Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI), 2018, p. 61 ff.)

⁵ These purposes are not identical to, but at least similar to, the activities of the Federal Statistical Office's 2012/13 Time Use Survey (Zeitverwendungserhebung, ZVE) with the eight categories "Personal area, physiological regeneration", "Employment", "Qualifications, education", "Household management and family care", "Volunteering, voluntary work, support for other households, gatherings", "Social life and entertainment", "Sport, hobbies, games" and "Media use".

For the 2022 survey, secondary activities as well as travelling times and means of transport will also be surveyed.

The seven journey purposes described and the eight time-use activities can be roughly categorised into three groups:

1. Functional activities related to the maintenance of daily life
2. Professional and educational activities related to working life and the necessary qualifications
3. Leisure as a residual category.

Table 1 shows an overview of the activity groups.

However, the specific categorisation can be debated. In particular, the ZVE activity category ‘Volunteering, voluntary work, supporting other households, gatherings’ can be viewed differently here: Participation in a demonstration (‘assembly’) or volunteering as part of an association can have a functional or leisure character, participation in a training event in voluntary work can belong to leisure time, but can also have (professional) qualifying content and be organised like a business trip.

“Physiological regeneration“ can have both a functional (‘sleep’) and a leisure-oriented character (‘boredom’) (Stengel, 1998).

Table 1: Activity groups and their counterparts in MiD and ZVE

Activity group	MiD	ZVE
Functional activities	Shopping, errands, accompaniment	Personal area, physiological regeneration; household management and care of the family; (voluntary work, voluntary commitment, support for other households, meetings)
Profession and education	Work, business, education	Employment; qualification, education
Leisure time	Leisure time	Social life and entertainment; sports, hobbies, games; media use

Travelling mobility

In a comprehensive study commissioned by the German Federal Environment Agency/Umweltbundesamt (UBA), Schulz et al. (2020) studied the environmental impact of travel in Germany.. The authors of the UBA study wanted to describe ‘tourism’ more comprehensively than other studies.⁶ They therefore argue: ”In order to capture a complete picture of travel mobility, it is necessary to analyse data from mobility surveys in everyday life.” (Schulz et al., 2020, p. 67). At first glance, this seems counterintuitive, as tourism is characterised by its non-everyday nature (as shown in the figure on page 70 of the same study).

⁶ Other notable studies in Germany are the FUR Reiseanalyse (which only looks at holiday trips) and the dwif-Tagesreisenmonitor (which only looks at day trips). From the outset, neither study claims to depict tourism as a whole.

To remedy this, the authors first form inclusive heuristics (Schulz et al., 2020, p. 68): Travelling mobility then comprises

- all reasons for travelling with an overnight stay (except for second homes),
- travel occasions without overnight stay with main activity leisure, holiday, private errands or a business occasion.

In addition, ‘tours’ consisting of one or more journeys and one or more activities are created from the available travel diaries for individual reporting days. Such a tour is assigned to travel mobility if it (Schulz et al., 2020, p. 109)

1. does not include any work or educational activity,
2. lasts at least 240 minutes,
3. exceeds a minimum distance (city: 30 km, medium-sized town 40 km, small town/village: 50 km)

The overall model is shown in Figure 2. Although the chosen approach is pragmatic (it can be used as a basis for estimating the emissions of travel defined in this way), it is not comprehensive. On the one hand, not all travel purposes or activities beyond work and education qualify a trip as travel or tourism. On the other hand, there may well be shorter trips in

terms of time and distance that could be categorised as travel or tourism. The same may apply to visits to a second home.⁷

Figure 2: Sequence of heuristics for the identification of motorhomes at tour level

Source: Schulz et al, 2020, p. 110

⁷ Especially in tourist centres, second homes are often held as an investment and then regularly rented out, so that the owner's visit is the tourist exception rather than the everyday rule.

Figure 3: A two-dimensional mobility model

Model

A two-dimensional model of mobility can be created from the dimensions described (continuum from everyday life to tourism and categories of functional activities, occupation and education as well as leisure) (Figure 3) with the aim of identifying the forms of mobility in tourism.

In the ‘functional activities/purposes’ category, the forms of tourism are quite limited: Medical tourism or certain forms of shopping tourism can be mentioned here. These are trips that have a clear function (for example, to have an operation performed by a particular expert or using a particular technique), but these trips can still have a tourist character; it is not for nothing that they are referred to as ‘medical tourism’ (Locher & Pforr, 2015). Interestingly, visiting a hospital in a neighbouring federal state is hardly considered medical tourism, whereas a sheikh visiting Germany for medical reasons is. Apparently, other aspects of mobility play a role here (distance, added value, accompaniment).

In the work and education category, the area designated as tourism is somewhat broader: in addition to typical business trips with their numerous occasions and forms (Sonntag et al., 2020) this can also include rehabilitation tourism in specialised clinics (the aim of these stays is to restore the ability to work, which is why they are classified under ‘work and training’). Clearly non-tourist forms of mobility in this category are commuting to work or education or the activities of people who are travelling for work (from truck drivers to pilots).

The yellow-coloured tourist area is broadest in leisure mobility: apart from regular walks or the trip to the sports or singing club, many things are classified as tourism here, such as the trip to the second home or to the permanent campsite, many types of day trips (Geiger & Bengsch,

2020; Harrer, 1995), visiting trips and holiday trips, regardless of their length. Bleisure trips, which are usually also categorised as tourism, can be found at the transition to work and education (Lichy & McLeay, 2018).

Implications

The results found so far have implications for the interface between transport and tourism research. It has become clear, for example, that analysing everyday journeys alone can only provide a blurred view of tourism or travel mobility. The survey of usage frequencies per mode of transport can lead to tourist mobility being overshadowed by everyday mobility, simply because it occurs less frequently.

There are also consequences for the modelling of traffic flows and needs: While a typical *daily routine* usually forms the basis of modelling for everyday mobility, it is more the typical *trip non-routine* for tourist mobility, which can, however, take very different forms. There are also demand-side differences in other aspects such as destinations, frequencies and distances (Table 2). When modelling and analysing

tourism mobility, these temporal, spatial and organisational characteristics should be taken into account⁸ :

Above all, however, it should have become clear that the boundaries between everyday mobility and tourist mobility are blurred. Although more or less broad tourist areas can be found depending on the purpose and activity, the classification of a route as tourist or non-tourist is sometimes dependent on the individual perspective of the traveller or researcher.

Table 2: Implications for modelling everyday mobility and tourist mobility

	Everyday mobility	Tourist mobility
In terms of time		
Modelling basis	Typical daily routine	Typical itinerary
Frequency	Relatively frequent	Rare
Regularity	Mostly regular	Rather irregular
Weekdays	Especially on weekdays	Day trips mainly on weekends and public holidays, holiday trips often start and end on Saturdays
Clock times	Peak in the early morning, midday and late afternoon	Later start, later end
Seasonality	Low	Higher seasonality (particularly frequent in summer, particularly rare in November, January and February)

⁸ Cf. also the demand-side framework conditions for tourist mobility, which are mentioned by the transport planning working group in the FGSV's „Hinweise zur Berücksichtigung des

Spatial		
Distance	Rather short	Rather long
Goals	Supply, work, education, everyday services	Destinations or tourist points of interest (PoI)
Regional knowledge	Relatively high	Rather low (because unknown destinations are travelled to more frequently)
Organisational		
Number of persons	Often alone	Mostly in company
Luggage	Rather little (except for shopping)	The longer the journey, the more luggage (suitcases, bags, ski equipment, surfboard, but also food, camping chairs, etc.)
Knowledge of timetables and fares	High for regular public transport users	Rather low even among regular public transport users
Weather dependency	Low	Stronger (not only the sun, but also snow and rain play a role)
Flexibility	Rather low	Relatively high (spontaneous decisions)
Experience-orientation	Very low	High (sometimes the journey is also the goal, especially on cycle tours or hikes)

Freizeitverkehrs bei der Gestaltung des ÖPNV“ (Forschungsgesellschaft für Straßen- und Verkehrswesen, 2021, p. 16).

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Notes

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